

A Study On Effect Of Failure Of Real Service Provider On Level Of Satisfaction With Aggregator Firm - A Case Study Of Zomato In Nagpur

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Zomato, Aggregator, Customer Satisfaction, Service Recovery And Service Failure</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5700916</p>	<p><i>Purpose:</i> The study helps to know how the level of satisfaction is affected by the failure of the actual service provider and aggregator. This study has been undertaken to bridge the gap between existing literature of customer satisfaction, service recovery and service failure and service providers, but this fulfilment of research gap is from the perspective of food supplier. The findings and conclusions may vary according to company and change in circumstances.</p> <p><i>Methodology/Approach:</i> The author had used questionnaire method for data collection. It was found in the study that perceived controllability and perceived stability creates an accountability for the aggregator firm. SPSS and MS-excel are used for data collection and analysis and IBM-AMOS is used for model development and model interpretation.</p> <p><i>Findings:</i> This study takes into consideration the controllability and responsibility of aggregator firm and it studies the impact of customer sense of power and perceived punishment on level of customer satisfaction.</p> <p><i>Research limitations/future scope:</i> There are many studies on customer satisfaction, but there is very less literature available in the area of service failure. This study is applied only into the business of hotel industry wherein Zomato is the aggregator but the same model can be applied into other services like laundry care, home delivery of medicine, cab services etc.</p> <p><i>Practical implications:</i> The findings and the model developed by the author can be used in the similar service organizations wherein aggregator model can be applied. Further, the academicians can use this study for literature review purpose and can apply some more parameters in the service recovery and service failure part and can take this study further.</p> <p><i>The Originality/value of paper:</i> Such kind of study wherein aggregator model is studied are rare. This study will act as a guide for the businesses who want to study their existing customer base to understand them better. Academicians can use this study for further research in the area of service recovery and service failure in aggregator models and can try to apply the findings and model in other service areas.</p>

Introduction

Zomato is present in Nagpur city for more than five years. It was a sunny day and Mr. Sharma wanted to order some food through Zomato, since it was late in night and Mr. Sharma was living all alone at his home. He was well informed that the delivery boy was not an employee of the restaurant nor he had cooked the food. The customer had a very intense dispute with the delivery person regarding the time of delivery. Mr. Sharma was very dissatisfied with the delivery person and started cursing him because Mr. Sharma felt that Zomato did not appoint proper delivery person. He also became angry with Zomato because he faced similar type of issues with Zomato in recent past number of times. Mr. Sharma complained Zomato regarding this. Zomato apologized for that incident and assured that they will not let this happen to him in future but they did not mention about any sort of punishment to the delivery person nor offered any sort of monetary compensation. This further made Mr. Sharma sad, unhappy and disappointed and decided to switch to Swiggy, the close competitor of Zomato.

The present study focuses on a service delivery situation such as the customer Mr. Sharma faced wherein a failure in service caused by the actual service provider leads to the expectation of service recovery and dissatisfaction with the aggregator. It has been observed in the market that aggregator business model has worked very well in the current scenario. In this model the aggregator can be considered as the connecting link between the customers and the real service providers with the use of various technological advancements, various available resources, information etc. thus it has reduced the various costs of the companies such as primary survey cost, process cost, cost associated with risk management etc.

Understanding the psychology of the customer in the aggregators model is one of the very important steps for every manager towards the growth of his business. Another important aspect is in the model of aggregator business eco-system of the aggregator as well as the real service provider are significant. The number of loyal registered customers and the number of registered service providers determines the strength of an aggregator.

Also, it is very important to understand the relationship between the service provider and its customers and the impact an aggregator has is very vital to study if one really wants to understand the aggregator business model.

This study also makes an effort to explain various drivers of recovery expectations of the customers and its impact on customer satisfaction. It is the reality that it is the primary responsibility of the aggregator to ensure accurate service recovery even if the service failure has occurred due to the real service provider since he the one who faces the customer predominantly all the time. Therefore, it is very essential for any aggregator to understand how to evaluate a customer and what are his/her expectations of service recovery, to an extent an effort has been made in this study to cover this aspect as well.

On the basis of the attribution theory, the usually the observed control of the aggregator and, the severity and consistency of the failure lead to expectation of recovery and dissatisfaction towards the aggregator. If the customer is powerful then also his power will have an impact on the recovery expectations.

Research Gap:

Many studies have been performed in the area of customer satisfaction, service recovery and service failure but very less studies have been conducted in the area of service aggregator. This study has been undertaken to bridge the gap between existing literature of customer satisfaction, service recovery and service failure and service providers, but this fulfilment of research gap is from the perspective of food supplier. The findings and conclusions may vary according to company and change in circumstances.

The following research gaps have been identified for the study:

Type of research Gap	Explanation
Evidence Gap (Contradictory Evidence Gap)	The researcher identified an apparent evidence gap in the prior research concerning service recovery. Previous research has addressed several aspects of customer satisfaction majorly: Javornik, Ana (2012), Soliman, Dr. Hisham Sayed (2011) talks about customer satisfaction. There are very less studies which are conducted on service failure aspect with respect to the aggregator business model. The researcher has identified there is an evidence gap in the prior studies that are contradictory in the findings [Miles, 2017].
Knowledge Gap (Knowledge Void Gap)	The researcher identified an apparent knowledge gap in the prior research concerning the area of service failure and aggregator business model. Though there are many studies conducted on customer satisfaction with respect to the service industry but service failure aspect was not covered. Hence this study will help to bridge the knowledge gap by studying the relationship between customers perception of power, his controllability and its ultimate impact on the aggregator in the form of monetary recovery as well as punishment.
Practical Knowledge Gap (Action-Knowledge Conflict Gap)	There appears to be a practical- knowledge gap in the prior research. This gap has occurred since not much was done prior on this subject matter and hence proper literature background cannot be created. There is no proper evidence for the impact of monetary recovery or punishment on the customer satisfaction level by keeping the customers sense of power in mind. This study had tried to make a noteworthy contribution in the field of service recovery model in the aggregators business.
Methodological Gap (Methodology Void Gap)	The researcher identified a methodological gap in the prior research. This study was undertaken by applying the AMOS research model to understand the customers level of satisfaction which he derives from the aggregator service provider. This model studied the various relationship of the variables with each other. The data was collected through questionnaire which was filled up by the customers and the customer feedback was also studied. Such kind of aggregator studies are rare and thus, the data collected
Empirical Gap (Evaluation Void Gap)	There is appears to be an empirical gap in the prior research. Since such kind of study was not conducted before. So very less literature is available on this background.
Theoretical Gap (Theory Application Void Gap)	The researcher identified an apparent theoretical gap in the prior research concerning service providers especially the aggregator business and their failure ratio. This is not

	a simple study on customer satisfaction rather a proper study of satisfaction of customer with respect to the aggregator business. Thus, tries to bridge this theoretical gap. However, an investigation in terms of model and theoretical development is necessary. An exhaustive study dealing with such issues carries much importance keeping the topics like customer satisfaction, customer perception and aggregator model in mind.
Population Gap (Under-researched Sub-Groups Gap)	Based on the review of the prior research, there is a population gap. Some of the customers opinion was not taken where as some customers have not given proper feedback or rating so the data was either missed out or incorrectly filled. A study of this group is important because they are in direct contact with the aggregator. Very little research has been done on the aggregator business model. So reference data is also not available.

Research Methodology:

For this study Quantitative Research methodology will be used since this study aims to achieve certain objectives and the data has to be collected from the customers of Zomato and Swiggy from Nagpur city. The questionnaire was filled up from the respondents and the partially filled questionnaires were rejected. Hypothesis for the study have been formed and will be tested. The data was gathered by using cluster random sampling since the cluster of customers of Zomato and Swiggy were created after interacting with the them and then randomly customers were picked up to fill the questionnaire. Data was analyzed by using SPSS software and model was developed by the researcher by using AMOS.

Research Problem:

As we all know that customer is the king and every company strives very hard to satisfy its king i.e. customer in every best possible way. Whenever it has been observed in the market that service has failed in certain aspects companies immediately took action towards putting efforts in rectifying the things which have went wrong while dealing with the customer. If the efforts are made in right direction in long run it may lead towards generating customer trust and build up organization reputation in market. This study has been undertaken in order to create a model and find out various drivers of recovery expectations of the customers and its impact on customer satisfaction

Type of research:

Exploratory Research

This study is conducted in order to explore the above stated research problem. Very few studies have been conducted in this area. Though this type of research may not help in getting exact solution to the stated problem but can help in providing certain leads and insights towards it. At times it also helps in laying down the foundation for future studies.

Objectives:

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To identify the major drivers of recovery expectations of the customers and its impact on customer satisfaction.
2. To understand consumer evaluations and expectations of service recovery and its importance to the aggregator.
3. To find out the impact of service failure on aggregator network.
4. To study the impact of service recovery strategies on consumer's revenge taking behaviour.

Hypothesis:

- H1. Controllability attributions regarding actual service provider failures are **positively** related to aggregator firm's responsibility.
- H2. Stability attributions regarding actual service provider failures are **positively** related to aggregator firm's responsibility.
- H3. Aggregator firm's responsibility for actual service provider failures has a **positive** impact on customer satisfaction.
- H4. A firm's responsibility for actual service provider failure has a **positive impact** on a customer's expected monetary compensation.
- H5. A firm's responsibility for actual service provider failure has a **positive impact** on a customer's expected punishment of actual service provider.
- H6. A customer's expected monetary compensation is **positive** related to customer satisfaction in the case of actual service provider failure.

H7. A customer’s expected punishment of actual service provider is **positive** related to customer satisfaction in the case of actual service provider failure.

Sample

Data was collected through google form collected which was circulated amongst the people who were from the age group of 30 to 60 years using smartphones. These respondents belong to income group ranging from middle to high. The respondents were either students or working professionals or businessmen from Nagpur. These respondents are regular user of aggregator business. For this study the researcher has approached 441 respondents in total. The actual respondents who have properly filled up the questionnaire was 390.

For the above model the values of the variables for Absolute fit Model are as follows:

Model Fit Indices	Recommended Values	Observed Value	Authors
Chi-square (CMIN/DF)	1-5	5.239	Bollen and Long (1993) and Kelloway (1995)
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	> 0.90	0.947	Byrne, 1994
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	> 0.90	0.987	Bollen, 1990
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	> 0.90	0.957	Bollen, 1990
Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	> 0.90	0.907	Hu and Bentler, 1998
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	> 0.90	0.956	Byrne, 1994
Root Mean Square Error of	< 0.08	0.000	Browne and Sugawara,

Approximation (RMSEA)			1996
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Impact of aggregator firm's responsibility on expected monetary compensation is positive ($\beta = .25$, $p < .001$) and significant, but more impact on expected punishment of actual service provider ($\beta = .56$, $p < .001$) and significant. This supports H4 and H5.

H4. A firm's responsibility for actual service provider failure has a **positive impact** on a customer's expected monetary compensation.

H5. A firm's responsibility for actual service provider failure has a **positive impact** on a customer's expected punishment of actual service provider.

Since impact of the variable controllability attribution is positive on aggregator firm's responsibility ($\beta = .52$, $p < .001$) and significant along with positive but not that significant impact of Stability attributions on aggregator firm's responsibility ($\beta = .11$, $p < .001$) as well as significant positive impact of Aggregator firm's responsibility on customer satisfaction ($\beta = .60$, $p < .001$) the first three hypothesis H1, H2 and H3 are held true.

H1. Controllability attributions regarding actual service provider failures are **positively** related to aggregator firm's responsibility.

H2. Stability attributions regarding actual service provider failures are **positively** related to aggregator firm's responsibility.

H3. Aggregator firm's responsibility for actual service provider failures has a **positive** impact on customer satisfaction.

Conclusion:

With the development of technology and increased used of smartphone amongst the users aggregator business model has got importance and relevance in various areas. In this model, aggregator firms bridge the gap between the actual service provider and consumers by decreasing the gaps associated to information irregularity, demand variations, quality guarantees, etc.

However often it was found that usually the firms using aggregator model keep the aggregator far away from the accountability of the consequences of the service connections. This ultimately affects the level of satisfaction of consumer.

In this research, the author had studied the particular situation where the failure of actual service provider creates an impact on the level of consumer satisfaction. Such kind of study are rare which have made an attempt to study consumer behaviour in the model set up of aggregator business.

The author had used questionnaire method for data collection. It was found in the study that perceived controllability and perceived stability creates an accountability for the aggregator firm. That means, if any case there is any kind of service failure the consumers will held aggregator responsible.

Managerial implication:

The study helps to know how the level of satisfaction is affected by the failure of the actual service provider and aggregator. It also proves that the aggregators are also affected by failure of actual service providers even if the terms and conditions does not hold the aggregator responsible.

Secondly, this study also demonstrates the significance of analysing consumer perceptions and his sense of power. Most of the aggregators use various ways of collecting the feedback of the customers. If the feedback given by the customers are analysed properly, we can get the actual understand of the customer perception and their experience about the aggregator and actual service provider. It also helps to know the actual reasons of service failures.

Also, should be taken to measure and analyse the sense of power of the customers. The sense of power of the customer may come from his social status, his profession, his relationships and networks etc.

Thirdly, if the sense of responsibility is high the compensation which he has to pay to customer (monetary compensation) is high and if the responsibility is low monetary compensation will also be low. If the monetary compensation is high the punishment given will be on a lower side and vice-versa. Many a times short term loss of customer can be compensated by punishment and long-term loss can be compensated by the monetary punishment. This decision of compensation is decided by the customer sense of power. So, it is important to understand and study the customers sense of power.

Lastly, we can say the impact of punishment decides the level of satisfaction for the customer.

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